

Theoretical investigations of synthesized Schiff base ligand derived from *S*-alkyldithiocarbazate

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Abstract : 4-Hydroxy-3-methoxy Schiff base derived from *S*-methylthiocarbazate was prepared adopting a novel method by condensation of *S*-methylthiocarbazate and 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde in ethanolic medium and characterized by various physico-chemical and spectral techniques such as elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, UV-Vis spectra and gas chromatography for structure determination. Fundamental vibrational frequencies, computed using four semi-empirical methods AM1, PM3, MNDO, MNDO/3 were compared with experimentally obtained vibrations. MNDO method gives the most satisfactory correlation between experimental and computed vibrational frequencies. Various parameters like net atomic charge and electron density were computed theoretically by MINDO/3, MNDO, PM3 and AM1 semi-empirical methods to elucidate its structure. The coordination sites observed by experimental data are in good agreement with computed data obtained by AM1 and PM3 methods. Out of two nitrogen atoms, azo-methine nitrogen carried more electron density.

Keywords : Schiff base ligand, semi-empirical, IR spectrum, UV-Vis spectrum, AM1, PM3, MNDO, MINDO/3 calculations.

Introduction

Dithiocarbazates exhibit significant antifungal, anti-protozoal, antibacterial, and anti-cancer activities. Recently an *in vitro* insulin-mimetic potential of these compound has been established¹. Carcinostatic activities have been found for metal complexes of dithiocarbazic acid and the Schiff base derived from *S*-methyl esters². Dithiocarbazic acid, its *N*-substituted derivatives as well as their Schiff bases derived from different carbonyl compounds have attracted the attention of investigators because of their interesting physico-chemical properties³⁻⁶ and potentially useful chemotherapeutic activities⁷⁻¹². Schiff bases of *S*-alkyldithiocarbazate and their metal complexes containing nitrogen and sulfur atoms have been found as potential drugs¹³⁻¹⁷.

Although a large number of studies involving complexes of these ligands with transition metal ions with different structures have been reported, there have been very fewer studies on theoretical investigations. Since the title ligand having different coordination sites is a potential bioactive compound, metal ions may approach the ligand in various ways to produce metal complexes with varying properties and applications. The title ligand 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde Schiff base of *S*-methylthiocarbazate was synthesized and theoretical studied by quantum chemical semi-empirical methods in order to elucidate the possible coordination sites and to establish the structure and stability of resulting complexes.

Semi-empirical methods are very useful tools for studying organic molecules and related structures as they provide researchers a relatively quick way of studying the

structure and behavior of molecules. Literature review reveals that various molecular properties of number of Schiff bases and their metal complexes have been studied by semi-empirical methods¹⁸⁻²⁰. These methods allow the valence electronic structure of molecules with appreciable saving in computational effort. The various semi-empirical approaches have been reviewed by Berthier²¹ and critically discussed by De Brouckere²².

Semi-empirical quantum chemical methods are based on the Hartree-Fock formalism, but make many approximations and obtain some parameters from empirical data. They are very important in computational chemistry for treating large molecules where the full Hartree-Fock method without the approximations is too expensive. The use of empirical parameters appears to allow some inclusion of electron correlation effects into the methods. The most common and popular semi-empirical methods used today are AM1 (Austin Model 1)^{23,24}, PM3 (Parametric Method 3)^{25,26}, MNDO (Modified Neglect of Differential Overlap)²⁷ and MINDO/3²⁸. These methods are designed to get the various properties like heat of formation, total energy, electronic energy, core-core repulsion energy, ionization potential, net atomic charge, electron density, vibrational frequency etc. of organic and inorganic molecules. Practically it is experienced that for a particular problem one of these methods proved to be remarkably better than others. They are all Self-Consistent

Field (SCF) methods, in which electrostatic repulsion and exchange stabilization are taken into account and all calculated integrals are evaluated by approximate means. In order to find out the most reliable methods for calculated geometry, the accuracy of those method in predicting vibrational frequencies of 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde Schiff base of *S*-methylthiocarbamate are determined by comparison with the corresponding experimental fundamental frequencies.

Results and discussion

When alkaline solution of hydrazine hydrate was added to CS₂, NH₂-NHCSSK (**1**) was formed which subsequently react with CH₃I to produce NH₂-NHCSSCH₃ (**2**), finally the product (**2**) react with vanillin to form the title ligand (**3**). The possible reaction steps are proposed in Scheme (A). In the IR spectrum (Fig. 1) the observed bands at 1599, 1290, 2854, 1097, 1205 and at 3543 cm⁻¹ are frequently assigned as ν(C=N), ν(C=S), ν(N-H), ν(N-N), ν(C-O) and ν(O-H) stretching vibrations, supporting the formation of title ligand (**3**).

Fig. 2 presents the ¹H NMR spectrum (in the solvent DMSO) of as prepared compound; the chemical shifts were recorded on δ scale (ppm) against TMS. The singlets observed at 3.7, 4.5, 9.6 and 13.2 ppm have readily been assigned as -CH₃ (3H), -OCH₃ (3H), -OH (1H, D₂O exchangeable) and -NH (1H, D₂O exchangeable). The

Fig. 1. IR spectrum of Schiff base ligand.

Fig. 2. ^1H NMR spectrum of Schiff base ligand.

multiplets between 7.2–7.4 are corresponding to 3H (Ar-H). ^{13}C NMR spectrum was recorded in order to establish the structure of above prepared Schiff base.

The observed peaks, in the decoupled ^{13}C NMR spectrum (Fig. 3) at $\delta(\text{C}=\text{S})$ 199 ppm, (C–H aromatic) 128.3 ppm, (CH_3) 58 ppm, (C–H aliphatic) 147.2 ppm support the formation of title Schiff base ligand (3).

The representative UV-Vis absorption spectrum of Schiff base ligand was recorded at room temperature and presented in Fig. 4. The sample was dissolved in DMSO. In the UV-Vis spectrum the band correspond to 311 nm is attributed to $n-\pi^*$ transition of the azomethine and the absorption band at 445 nm may be assigned CT transition which encroaches on visible region imparting colour of the ligand^{29,30}.

The purity of the Schiff base ligand was verified by GC analysis and the chromatogram is shown in Fig. 5. The title ligand 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde Schiff base of *S*-methyldithiocarbazate was dissolved in DMSO. In the gas chromatogram the major peak at 3.367 min (99.7% area) has been observed compared to that of solvent at 3.023 min (0.30%), indicating the synthesised compound is chiefly composed of the title ligand.

The experimental and calculated IR absorption bands for Schiff base ligand are shown in Table 1. The computed bands by AM1, PM3, MNDO and MINDO/3 methods are graphically depicted in Fig. 6. To examine the usefulness of the calculation method for IR, linearity between the experimental and calculated vibrations has been derived by plotting the experimental versus computed

Fig. 3. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of Schiff base ligand.

Fig. 4. UV-Vis spectrum of Schiff base ligand.

Fig. 5. Gas chromatogram of Schiff base ligand.

Table 1. Computed heat of formations, total energy, electronic energies, core-core repulsion energies and ionization potentials of Schiff base ligand (thione form)

Parameter	AM1	PM3	MNDO	MINDO/3
Heat of formation (kcal)	-40.38061	-39.35548	-64.94528	-119.71049
Total energy (eV)	-2875.42856	-2638.31170	-2951.36551	-2904.52097
Electronic energy (eV)	-15576.64084	-15110.95361	-15628.34565	-15073.54793
Core-core repulsion energy (eV)	12701.21228	12472.64191	12676.98015	12169.02696
Ionization potentials (eV)	4.20546	4.35399	3.87055	3.49328

vibrations and correlation coefficient has been analyzed. Graphical correlation between experimental and computed results are shown in Fig. 7.

Matching the simulated spectra with experimental counterparts may be useful for the compound identification particularly in case where screening of several possible isomers is necessary, than the detailed analysis of calculated spectra. Simulated and experimentally observed IR spectra of the Schiff base ligand (4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde Schiff base of *S*-methylthiocarbazate) are

presented in Table 1. The simulated spectra obtained by MNDO method are in good agreement for all IR bands viz. $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$, $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$, $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$, $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$. Some of the vibrational frequencies obtained in the computed spectra could not be identified in the experimental counterparts, possibly due to systematic errors between calculated and experimental value and neglect of anharmonicity and correlation. The correlation coefficient obtained for AM1, PM3, MNDO and MINDO/3 methods are 0.959, 0.962, 0.977 and 0.969 respectively. It is

Fig. 6. The simulated IR spectra for the Schiff base ligand.

Fig. 7. Graphical correlation between experimental and calculated IR frequencies.

evident that MNDO method gives the most satisfactory correlation between experimental and vibrational frequencies.

The geometries of Schiff base ligand were optimized using AM1, PM3, MNDO and MINDO/3 semi-empirical methods. Two isomers, namely enol and keto forms of the Schiff base ligand are possible (Figs. 5a and 5b). The optimized geometrical parameters of keto and enol forms

of Schiff base ligand are represented in Tables from 2 to 7. The 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde Schiff base of *S*-methylthiocarbamate has the -N(H)C(S) (thioamide) function and therefore, in principle, it can exhibit thione (Fig. 8a) and thiol (Fig. 8b) tautomerism.

These two forms of ligand can interact with metal ions in different ways to form metal complexes with different properties³¹⁻³⁶. Semi-empirical molecular quantum

Fig. 8. (a) Thione and (b) thiol form of Schiff base ligand.

mechanical methods are approximate methods but these serve the purpose of calculation of wave function, energy and other properties like ionization potential, heat of formation, molecular geometry, force constant, electron density distribution and interpretation of molecular spectra.

The computed heat of formation, total energy, electronic energy, core-core repulsion energy and ionization potential by AM1, PM3, MNDO and MINDO/3 methods are listed in Tables 2 and 3. Applying AM1, PM3, MNDO and MINDO/3 methods, heat of formation for the Schiff base ligand for thione form, were computed as -40.38061, -39.35548, -64.94528, -119.71049 kcal respectively

(Table 1), and for thiol form as -37.92094, -39.61715, -65.61487, -110.95492 kcal respectively, suggesting an exothermic synthesis.

The ionization potential energies (eV) of the ligand, for thione form are determined as 4.20546 (AM1), 4.35399 (PM3), 3.87055 (MNDO), 3.49328 (MINDO/3) (Table 1), however from MNDO/3 it was 3.4 eV, suggesting its donating power. For any ligand, to be used for formation of a stable complex, the most common requirement is to locate the bonding site, with which the metal ion will react. For this purpose, the net atomic charge and electron density are the useful parameters to look into the

Table 2. Computed heat of formations, total energy, electronic energies, core-core repulsion energies and ionization potentials of Schiff base ligand (thiol form)

Parameters	AM1	PM3	MNDO	MINDO/3
Heat of formation (kcal)	-37.92094	-39.61715	-65.61487	-110.95492
Total energy (eV)	-2888.97763	-2653.65564	-2965.56013	-2918.90575
Electronic energy (eV)	-16034.52922	-15574.84761	-15980.16478	-15226.52389
Core-core repulsion energy (eV)	13145.55160	12921.19196	13014.60465	12307.61814
Ionization potentials (eV)	2.36120	2.58840	2.46800	2.66739

Table 3. Computed net atomic charges for Schiff base ligand (thione form)

Atom	AM1	PM3	MNDO	MNDO/3
N8	-0.0640	0.0045	-0.0951	0.0220
N9	-0.2665	-0.2579	-0.3255	-0.1348
S11	0.0022	-0.0824	0.0195	-0.4815
S12	-0.4301	-0.5178	-0.3969	-0.6514
O14	-0.2194	-0.1965	-0.2803	-0.3980
O16	-0.2664	-0.2340	-0.2556	-0.4460

possible coordination sites of a ligand, and therefore to predict the stability of the complex.

Net atomic charge (Table 3 and Table 4) and electron density (Table 5 and Table 6) have been calculated by AM1, PM3, MNDO, MNDO/3 methods. In the Schiff base (Fig. 9) there are six atoms N8, N9, S11, S12, O14 and O16 which may be coordinated during complex formation with transition metal ion. From the previously

Table 4. Computed net atomic charges for Schiff base ligand (thiol form)

Atom	AM1	PM3	MNDO	MINDO/3
N8	-0.2063	-0.1898	-0.2485	0.0488
N9	-0.1086	-0.0459	-0.1419	-0.0943
S11	0.1518	0.0444	0.1140	-0.4746
S12	-0.0788	0.0198	0.1046	-0.4989
O14	-0.2166	-0.1927	-0.2750	0.3987
O16	-0.2740	-0.2423	-0.2648	-0.4470

Table 5. Computed electron densities for Schiff base ligand (thione form)

Atom	AM1	PM3	MNDO	MINDO/3
N8	5.0640	4.9955	5.0951	4.9780
N9	5.2665	5.2579	5.3255	5.1348
S11	5.9978	6.0824	5.9805	6.4815
S12	6.4301	6.5178	6.3969	6.6514
O14	6.2194	6.1965	6.2803	6.3980
O16	6.2664	6.2340	6.2556	6.4460

reported experimental data, it is evident that N8, S12 and O16 are the coordination sites during complex formation which is further supported by thiol form of Schiff base ligand indicating that the ligands converted into thiol form

Table 6. Computed electron densities for Schiff base ligand (thiol form)

Atom	AM1	PM3	MNDO	MINDO/3
N8	5.2063	5.1898	5.2485	4.9512
N9	5.1086	5.0459	5.1419	5.0943
S11	5.8482	5.9556	5.8860	6.4746
S12	5.9212	5.9802	5.8954	6.4989
O14	6.2166	6.1927	6.2750	6.3987
O16	6.2740	6.2423	6.2648	6.4470

in the presence of metal salts in suitable medium. The net atomic charges and electron densities calculated by AM1, PM3 and MNDO supports the interaction of metal ion with thiol form of the ligand. The two methods AM1, and MNDO (electron densities between O14 and O16 are negligible) support N8, S12 and O16 as a coordination sites whereas MINDO/3 methods support N9, S12 and O16 as coordination site.

$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$, and $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ experimental vibrational frequency are more correlated to computed frequency of MNDO/3 method whereas $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ experimental vibrational frequency showing correlation with computed frequency of MNDO.

Fig. 9. Molecular structure of Schiff base ligand showing atomic numbering.

Table 7. Experimental and computed vibrational frequencies (cm⁻¹) of Schiff base ligand

IR bands	Experimental	AM1	PM3	MNDO	MINDO/3
v(C=N)	1599	1873	1775	1883	1647
v(C=S)	1097	913	915	1137	976
v(N-H)	2854	3334	3231	3522	3726
v(N-N)	1097	-	1274	1502	1195
v(C-O)	1205	1423	1065	1269	1259
v(O-H)	3752	3446	3670	3797	3781

Experimental

S-Methyldithiocarbazate was prepared by reported method³⁷. The title compound 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy Schiff base derived from *S*-methyldithiocarbazate was prepared adopting a novel route by condensation of ethanolic solution of *S*-methyldithiocarbazate (0.1 mol) and equimolar solution of 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde in the same solvent. The solution was heated on a steam bath for 2–3 h and then cooled to 0 °C in an ice bath. Precipitated Schiff base was filtered, washed, recrystallized with ethanol and dried at room temperature. Elemental analysis of Schiff base ligand was done on Elementar vario EL III Carlo Erba 1108. The IR spectrum of the Schiff base ligand was recorded on Perkin-Elmer Spectrum RX 1 FT IR spectrophotometer using KBr pallatisation technique. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker DRX-300 NMR spectrophotometer. UV-Vis absorption spectrum was recorded on UV-2450 (Shimadzu) spectrophotometer. Gas chromatograph was observed on Perkin-Elmer Autosystem XL instrument in the solvent DMSO.

Yield : 69%; m.p. 165 °C; Anal. (%) Found : N, 11.2; S, 24.4%. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₂N₂S₂ : N, 10.9; S, 25%.

Calculations

Semi-empirical calculations have been carried out using the MOPAC³⁸ package. Studies were done using personal computer, Core 2 Duo with 2.0 GHz processor, 250 GB hard disk and 3 GB RAM. The structure of the molecule were drawn on the PCMODEL package of Serena software³⁹ and optimized which is used as input for MOPAC. These calculations were done for the compound shown in Fig. 9.

Conclusion

Summarily, the structure of the 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy Schiff base derived from *S*-methyldithiocarbazate, synthesized by a new proposed route has been established by physico-chemical and spectral analysis. The simulated and observed IR bands are in good agreement the identification of the compound 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde Schiff base of *S*-methyldithiocarbazate. The physical parameters like heat of formations, total energy, electronic energies, core-core repulsion energies and ionization potentials are computed for the Schiff base ligand by semi-empirical AM1, PM3, MNDO, MINDO/3 methods. It is evident from the net atomic charges and electronic density values that N8, S12, O16, sites are available for coordination in thiol form of the ligand which is in agreement with experimental data. Heat of formation of ligand for thiol form by AM1, PM3, MNDO and MINDO/3 methods suggests it is exothermic and gives more satisfactory result with experimental data. Experimental vibrational frequency are more correlated to computed frequency of MNDO/3 method. Semi-empirical AM1, PM3, MNDO, MNDO/3 method gives the correlation coefficient between experimental and theoretical data for vibrational studies in order of 0.959, 0.962, 0.977 and 0.969 respectively. MNDO method gives more satisfactory correlation.

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